

Tracer diffusion of potassium and related parameters in three soils of West Bengal

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Tracer diffusion studies have been conducted in three soils of West Bengal, belonging to different soil order and having contrasting properties, in order to obtain the apparent tracer-diffusion coefficient of K by following the standard half-cell technique. The effects of changes in soil moisture content, bulk density, temperature, background electrolyte and tracer : background cationic concentrations on apparent diffusion coefficient are ascertained. These coefficients registered an increase with increasing bulk density, temperature, tracer level and also for NaCl background electrolyte, compared to CaCl₂ background electrolyte. The energy of activation, Arrhenius frequency factor and entropy factor of diffusion are evaluated for K-diffusion in the given soils. The trends of findings have been explained in terms of the detailed interactions, which, in turn, are characterized by nature of the given diffusion medium.

Diffusion is the process by which matter, as a result of its random molecular motion, is transported from one part of the system to another. It is the main process by which a nutrient ion moves through soil to the plant root surface. The diffusion coefficient of the nutrient ions gives valuable information towards the solute movement through soil, and hence is directly connected to soil fertility evaluation¹. Such diffusion coefficients are affected by various factors, such as bulk density, soil water content, concentration of a particular nutrient, soil temperature and other physical and chemical process that occur in soils. True self-diffusion coefficient cannot be investigated experimentally owing to the indistinguishability of the molecules². Tracer-diffusion is indeed diffusion of a single component, present in small concentration, in a large excess of other components. Such diffusion coefficients can be useful to evaluate several associated parameters of diffusion which provide additional information in regard to the mechanism of the diffusion process in soils at the molecular level. These parameters include the energy of activation (E_a), entropy factor of diffusion (σ) and Arrhenius frequency factor (A). This paper reports the results of a set of experiments conducted using soils, belonging to Inceptisol and Alfisol order, to find out the apparent tracer-diffusion coefficient (D_a) of potassium (K), along with the above mentioned associated diffusion parameters for the given diffusion process in the soils under study.

Results and Discussion

The important physicochemical properties of the soil samples are presented in Table 1. The results of effects of soil moisture content, bulk density and temperature on apparent diffusion coefficient (D_a) of K, having two tracer : background electrolytes concentration ratio, against two

different background electrolytes are presented in Tables 2 and 3. These results show that D_a values generally increase with increase of tracer : background cationic ratio. Since the nature and extent of interactions, retaining K in soil, may change with tracer levels³, and a higher concentration of background electrolyte may have hindered the effective passage of K from the tagged to untagged core⁴, such increases in D_a values could be expected.

Table 1. Important physicochemical properties of soils

Property	Location of soils		
	Baruipur Typic Ustochrept	Canning (acidic) Typic Haplaquept	Kashipur Typic Haplustalf
Taxonomic classification			
pH (1 : 2.5)			
Soil : Water	5.69	4.40	5.83
EC (d Sm ⁻¹)			
(1 : 5 :: Soil : Water)	0.190	1.70	0.043
CEC [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	22.5	20.3	4.72
Organic carbon			
(g kg ⁻¹)	21.6	18.5	5.16
Sand (%)	3.9	4.7	83.5
Silt (%)	28.3	44.4	5.5
Clay (%)	67.8	50.9	11.0
Texture	Clay	Silty clay	Loamy sand
Exchangeable (Ca ²⁺ + Mg ²⁺) [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	6.18	4.38	0.770
Exchangeable Na ⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	1.23	5.22	0.150
Exchangeable K ⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	0.416	0.621	0.143
Apparent density (Mg m ⁻³)	1.08	1.10	1.59
Absolute specific gravity	2.07	2.50	2.34
Maximum water holding capacity (%)	54.8	55.4	21.9
Pore space (%)	56.0	60.7	34.3

In all cases, the D_a values register an increase with increasing bulk density. As the bulk density increases, the diffusion path become less tortuous, because the air-pockets are removed and the crumbs are pressed into contact⁵, resulting in an increase in D_a values. The D_a values decrease with a decrease in soil moisture content. As the soil water content decreases, the cross-sectional area available for diffusion becomes smaller. This causes the path-length to increase, with the viscosity and negative adsorption becoming more important, as the water films decrease in thickness⁶, thereby causing a fall in D_a values. Furthermore, in nearly all the cases, the D_a values were comparatively higher in the Na^+ -saturated soils than in the corresponding Ca^{2+} -saturated soils (Table 2 and 3). Such increase of D_a values may possibly be attributed to the difficulty of K^+ to replace Ca^{2+} compared to Na^+ in the exchange phase of the given soils. A rise in temperature increases the corresponding D_a values for K in the given soils (Tables 2 and 3). Such rise may be attributed to the higher probability of the diffusing species at a higher temperature over-rolling the activation energy hill more readily, due to the concomitant greater kinetic energy content of diffusing K.

The values of the energy of activation (E_a), the Arrhenius frequency factor (A) and entropy factor of diffusion (σ) under different treatments in the given soils were computed, and are presented in Table 4. The E_a values decrease in nearly all the soils with increase in tracer background ratio at lower bulk density (Table 4) in both Ca^{2+} - and Na^+ -saturated soils, suggesting a facilitated diffusion of K at a

higher bulk density. The order of K ionic mobility in the clay interlayer space was found to be : kaolinite > illite > montmorillonite > vermiculite⁷. Indeed, Kashipur soil, being rich in kaolinite, has the highest E_a value (Table 4). The K^+ ions oscillate in the vicinity of a pair of exchange sites. The magnitude of the effective oscillation volume determines the energy barrier of exchange, and hence the energy of activation of the given process⁸. In illite and smectite, most exchangeable ions are in the interlayer positions. As one would possibly expect in view of the facilitated K-diffusion at a higher bulk density, the E_a values would show a declining trend with increasing bulk density, as was observed in the majority of cases (data not shown). Some deviations from this trend, however, suggest the interplay of other factors which may possibly influence E_a .

The Arrhenius frequency factor is defined as the probability of ion interaction which includes the frequency of oscillations that an ion undergoes at a given exchange site. In the present investigation, the A and σ values decrease in nearly all the treatment combinations with increasing tracer component. The lower values of A may be explained by higher probability of ion-exchange preceding diffusion at a higher tracer level.

The entropy factor of diffusion (σ) was interpreted⁸ according to the theory of absolute reaction rate. Thus σ (i.e. $[d^2 \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R)]^{1/2}$) depends on two factors, namely, (i) the equilibrium jump distance (d) encountered in diffusion in soil, and (ii) the accompanying entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger). Either abnormally large or small values of σ may lead to an indication as to the mechanism of diffusion. Large positive values of ΔS^\ddagger may suggest that the diffusion is accom-

Table 2. Effect of soil moisture content, bulk density and temperature on apparent tracer diffusion coefficient of K in three Ca^{2+} -saturated soils having two different tracer : background electrolyte concentration ratios

Tracer : background cationic ratio	Soil water content % WHC*	Bulk density mg m^{-3}	Temp. K	Apparent tracer-diffusion coefficient of K in soils ($D_a \times 10^{10}$) / $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$		
				Baruipur	Canning (acidic)	Kashipur
1 : 32	100	0.99	297	1.23	1.15	0.786
1 : 32	100	0.99	308	1.42	1.33	1.02
1 : 32	100	1.08	297	1.41	1.21	0.938
1 : 32	100	1.08	308	1.58	1.41	1.07
1 : 32	85	0.99	297	1.08	1.01	0.640
1 : 32	85	0.99	308	1.28	1.21	0.664
1 : 32	85	1.08	297	1.36	1.13	0.718
1 : 32	85	1.08	308	1.51	1.29	0.819
1 : 16	100	0.99	297	1.37	1.23	0.914
1 : 16	100	0.99	308	1.55	1.38	1.07
1 : 16	100	1.08	297	1.47	1.36	0.978
1 : 16	100	1.08	308	1.81	1.48	1.22
1 : 16	85	0.99	297	1.09	1.11	0.696
1 : 16	85	0.99	308	1.39	1.26	0.835
1 : 16	85	1.08	297	1.42	1.17	0.739
1 : 16	85	1.08	308	1.68	1.36	0.926

*WHC = Water holding capacity of soil.

Table 3. Effect of soil moisture content, bulk density and temperature on apparent tracer diffusion coefficient of K in three Na⁺-saturated soils having two different tracer : background electrolyte concentration ratios

Tracer :	Soil water content % WHC*	Bulk density Mg m ⁻³	Temp. K	Apparent tracer-diffusion coefficient of K in soils ($D_a \times 10^{10}$) / m ² s ⁻¹		
				Baruipur	Canning (acidic)	Kashipur
1:32	100	0.99	297	1.38	1.29	0.839
1:32	100	0.99	308	1.63	1.37	1.05
1:32	100	1.08	297	1.39	1.34	0.978
1:32	100	1.08	308	1.79	1.45	1.15
1:32	85	0.99	297	1.35	1.15	0.673
1:32	85	0.99	308	1.48	1.25	0.704
1:32	85	1.08	297	1.44	1.27	0.730
1:32	85	1.08	308	1.59	1.31	0.863
1:16	100	0.99	297	1.40	1.31	1.02
1:16	100	0.99	308	1.63	1.41	1.20
1:16	100	1.08	297	1.47	1.44	1.11
1:16	100	1.08	308	1.89	1.59	1.28
1:16	85	0.99	297	1.39	1.24	0.704
1:16	85	0.99	308	1.60	1.29	0.860
1:16	85	1.08	297	1.43	1.28	0.794
1:16	85	1.08	308	1.61	1.36	0.984

*WHC = Water holding capacity of soil.

panied by breakage of bonds, or by significant structural changes, while appreciable negative values may imply a partial immobilization of the diffusing species or solvent effects⁹. The σ values (Table 4) reveal that in most of the cases (except for Kashipur soil), it lies within the range of 0.644 to 2.95×10^{-11} m which is rather low as compared to the value for pure water (5.5×10^{-11} m)¹⁰. The ΔS^\ddagger for the self-diffusion of K⁺ is close to zero in pure water⁹. The *net* entropy of activation is regarded as the resultant of two opposing effects : (i) a positive contribution arising from the disturbance in diffusion environment by the diffusing ion, and (ii) a negative contribution from the electrostriction of water accompanying the separation of charge in forming the activated complex. Effect (i) may be expected to predominate when the diffusing ion is large, and when its association with the anionic exchange group is slight. In the present case, the effect (ii) tends to predominate due to the higher degrees of solvation of Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ ions which were exchanged for K⁺ ion, having a lower ionic potential (as the present K⁺ diffusion could be visualized as a K⁺/Ca²⁺ or K⁺/Na⁺ exchange for the two background electrolytes used). Hence such negative value of ΔS^\ddagger would obviously bring down σ . The σ values are generally lower for CaCl₂ background electrolyte at a particular tracer level than those for the corresponding NaCl background electrolyte. This substantiates the above hypothesis in view of a higher polarizing power of Ca²⁺ than that of Na⁺. The generally lower σ values for the given electrolyte at the higher tracer level also subscribes to this hypothesis as the enhanced K⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange at a higher tracer level would lead to a more negative value of ΔS^\ddagger . These findings are in agreement with earlier observations¹¹.

Table 4. Effect of tracer : background ratio and nature of background electrolytes on energy of activation (E_a), arrhenius frequency factor (A) and entropy factor of diffusion (σ) in soils at 100% water holding capacity and a bulk density of 0.99 Mg m⁻³ (d)

Location of soils	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$10^9 A$	Entropy factor of diffusion $10^{11} \sigma \times m$
Ca ²⁺ -saturated soils with tracer : background ratio = 1 : 32 :			
Baruipur	27.1	6.92	2.03
Canning (acidic)	27.5	6.80	2.01
Kashipur	49.3	118	8.37
Na ⁺ -saturated soils with tracer : background ratio = 1 : 32 :			
Baruipur	31.5	14.7	2.95
Canning (acidic)	11.4	0.698	0.644
Kashipur	42.4	45.4	5.19
Ca ²⁺ -saturated soils with tracer : background ratio = 1 : 16 :			
Baruipur	23.3	4.37	1.61
Canning (acidic)	21.7	3.10	1.36
Kashipur	29.8	7.61	2.13
Na ⁺ -saturated soils with tracer : background ratio = 1 : 16 :			
Baruipur	28.7	9.99	2.43
Canning (acidic)	13.9	1.03	0.782
Kashipur	30.7	9.75	2.41

Experimental

Surface soil samples (0–0.15 m) were collected from three different locations of West Bengal (Table 1) having contrasting soil characteristics, and duly processed (<2 mm). The important physicochemical properties of these soils were studied by using the standard methods¹².

A bulk amount of soil was equilibrated with calcium chloride and sodium chloride separately leading to a cationic concentration of 3.2 g kg⁻¹ soil for each cation in

the homoionic soils. As Ca^{2+} and Na^+ ions have limiting ionic conductances of the same order of magnitude as the K^+ ion, they were used as background cations for the given diffusion study. Potassium chloride was added to one-half of the Ca- and Na-equilibrated soils to have two different K levels of 0.1 and 0.2 g kg^{-1} of soil, respectively. The half-cell technique¹³ was adopted for diffusion study and the apparent diffusion coefficient (D_a) of K was calculated¹⁴,

$$D_a = \pi l^2 f^2 / t \quad (1)$$

where l is the length of each half-cell and f the fraction of the tracer ion (K^+) which had diffused in time t (s) from the tagged to untagged half-cell, and is obtained as : $f =$ amount of K in the initially untagged half-cell in time t / sum of amount of K in both tagged and untagged half-cells in time t .

For the purpose of this investigation, one half of the diffusion cell was packed with only background electrolyte treated soil, while the other half-cell with background and tracer equilibrated soil at the desired bulk density and moisture content. The two half-cells were gently brought into contact and were held in position by tightening the screws across the supporting pair of bakelite sheets. Due care was taken to maintain the joint cells in water-leakproof condition, while being kept inside an incubator for the requisite period of diffusion at the desired temperature (T). The cells were dismantled after 6 days¹⁵, and K from the soil in each half-cell was extracted with distilled water, and K in the aqueous soil extracts was measured flame photometrically. The diffusion experiments were conducted for each tracer : background cation ratio (1 : 32 and 1 : 16) and for each background electrolyte (CaCl_2 and NaCl) at 100% and 85% water holding capacity soil moisture content, two bulk densities (0.99 and 1.08 Mg m^{-3}) and two temperatures, namely, 297 and 308 K, in each soil.

The D_a values obtained were used in the relationships (eqs. 2-4), derived from the Eyring's theory of absolute reaction rate¹⁶, for obtaining several associated parameters. Thus,

$$D_a = (ekT/h)d^2 \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R) \exp(-E_a/RT) \quad (2)$$

where e is the base of natural logarithm, k the Boltzmann constant; h the Planck's constant, d the average distance between equilibrium positions during diffusion, ΔS^\ddagger the entropy of activation E_a the energy of activation, R the universal gas constant and T the absolute temperature. The parameter, $[d^2 \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R)]^{1/2}$, is designated as entropy fac-

tor of diffusion (σ)⁸.

E_a was calculated^{8,17} as follows :

$$\log D_a = \log A - (E_a/2.303 RT) \quad (3)$$

where A is the Arrhenius frequency factor.

It follows from eq. (3),

$$\log \frac{(D_a)_{T_1}}{(D_a)_{T_2}} = \frac{E_a}{2.303 R} \left[\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right] \quad (4)$$

where $(D_a)_{T_1}$ and $(D_a)_{T_2}$ refer to apparent tracer-diffusion coefficient of K in soils at absolute temperatures T_1 and T_2 , respectively. By substituting these values in eq. (4), E_a was obtained, and with the knowledge of E_a the value of A could be obtained for diffusion of K in a given soil using eq. (3).

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